

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND ACHIEVEMENT IN COMMERCE OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

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Abstract:

Emotional intelligence has been attracting researchers in these days considering its relative significance to succeed in personal, professional and social life. Commerce, that deals with trade and related services have become an added value course in the growing world of trade flourishing. In this context, the present research aims at investigating the level of academic achievement and finding out whether there is any significant difference among the higher secondary students studying commerce with regard to certain demographic variables. The applied survey research was conducted on a sample of 850 higher secondary students (492 male & 358 female) chosen from 20 schools. Emotional Intelligence Scale developed by Shailendra Singh (2004) was used to assess emotional intelligence. A self-constructed and validated tool 'Achievement Test in Commerce' by the investigator with 50 statistically selected objective type questions (out of 80) was used for the study. The results of the descriptive analysis showed that the level of emotional intelligence and achievement in commerce of higher secondary students is average. The differential analysis result, t-test showed that there was no significant difference in emotional intelligence and academic achievement in commerce with regard to gender, locality of students. The correlational analysis shows that there is significant positive correlation between emotional intelligence and achievement in commerce of higher secondary students.

Key Words: Emotional intelligence, Achievement in commerce, Higher secondary students

Introduction:

Education is a process of gaining knowledge, refining attitudes and developing skills. It is a continuum and an on-going process and begins formally in school education. School education is the foundation and students are running-a-race to be the toppers competing each other. Academic achievement is the ultimate aim of all the takes stakeholders of education. Teachers are professionals, well-trained and play an important role in academic deliveries. Teachers are the single most important element of the school system ((NKC, 2006, p.43). Emotional intelligence is one of the factors that affect the students on the whole and its impact pervades in all that is done by the students and in-relation with peers and teachers. This article investigates the relationship between emotional intelligence and achievement in commerce of higher secondary students.

Need and Significance of the Study:

The activities involved in buying and selling things is commerce (Cambridge Dictionary). It is the exchange of goods and services, especially on a large scale. Commerce education is a branch of knowledge which provides experience of business world at a large and in all its manifestations to its learners and this is basically meant to provide the students in-depth knowledge of different functional areas of business and allied activities to mould the learners according to the dynamic requirements of the trade, commerce and industry (Mishra, 2017). It is "the backbone of business" (Aruna & Sharmila, 2015). The commerce group is much preferred and is on-demand at all higher secondary schools at present to the extent that institutions have come up exclusively for teaching commerce at varying levels. Commerce provides all the goods that we need and it is carried out in relationship with other human beings. A high emotional intelligence helps to maintain a state of harmony in oneself and finally be more self-confident in dealing with the challenges of living and learning in educational institutions (Roy, Sinha & Suman, 2013). In this context, emotional intelligence has its own significant role in making commerce and trade a success, and it all begins in school education. Higher secondary education is decides the future employment and hence, academic achievement is of greater significance for the higher secondary students. The investigator being a teacher educator in a college of education teaching commerce at present is interested in finding out the "Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Achievement in Commerce of Higher Secondary Students". The findings of the study would be helpful for the students pursuing commerce at school level. Hence is this study.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To find out the level of emotional intelligence and academic achievement of higher secondary commerce students

2. To find out whether there is any significant difference between male and female higher secondary commerce students in their emotional intelligence and academic achievement.
3. To find out whether there is any significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary commerce students in their emotional intelligence and academic achievement.
4. To find out whether there is any significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of higher secondary commerce students.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- H₀1: The level of level of emotional intelligence and academic achievement of higher secondary commerce students is average.
- H₀2: There is no significant difference between male and female higher secondary commerce students in their emotional intelligence and academic achievement.
- H₀3: There is no significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary commerce students in their emotional intelligence and academic achievement.
- H₀4: There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of higher secondary commerce students.

Methodology:

The researcher used survey method for the present study. The total sample comprises 850 higher secondary students (492 male & 358 female) chosen from 20 schools (9 government, 5 aided & 6 private) using simple random sampling technique, from Kanchipuram district, Tamil Nadu, India. ‘Emotional Intelligence Scale’ developed and standardized by Shailendra Singh (2004) with 60 statements grouped under 5 dimensions (self-awareness, Self-regulation, Motivation, Social-awareness and Social skills) with 12 statements was used. Each item has five response options, namely Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Undecided, Agree and Strongly Agree, with the corresponding score value of 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5. The range of minimum score is 60 and the maximum is 300. A self-constructed and validated tool ‘Achievement Test in Commerce’ by the investigator with 50 selected objective type questions (from the 80 items of the pilot study) was used for the study. The right answer was given one mark and the wrong answer was given zero mark and the total scores could range from zero to fifty. The collected data were subjected to percentage analysis, t-test and F-test using SPSS, leading to infer the findings of the study.

Analysis of the Data:

Descriptive Analysis:

- H₀1: The level of emotional intelligence and academic achievement of higher secondary students is average.

Table 1: Level of emotional intelligence and academic achievement of higher secondary students

Variable	N	Mean	S.D.	M+1 S.D.	N-1S.D.	Level
Emotional Intelligence	850	147	24.3	171.3	122.7	Average
Achievement in Commerce		61	11.4	72.4	49.6	Average

Table 1 shows that the Mean score of Emotional intelligence of higher secondary students is 147 and Standard Deviation is 24.3. The Mean score lies between the Mean+1S.D. score (171.3) and M-1S.D. score (122.7), revealing that the level of achievement in commerce of higher secondary students is average.

The mean score in achievement in commerce of higher secondary students is 61 and Standard Deviation is 11.4. The Mean score lies between the Mean+1S.D. score (72.4) and M-1S.D. score (49.6), revealing that the level of achievement in commerce of higher secondary students is average.

Differential Analysis:

- H₀2: There is no significant difference between male and female higher secondary students in their emotional intelligence and academic achievement.

Table 2: Difference between male and female higher secondary students in their emotional intelligence and academic achievement

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Remarks
Emotional Intelligence	Male	492	154.2	16.7	0.478	NS
	Female	358	165.8	21.2		
Achievement in Commerce	Male	492	57.4	11.3	1.46	NS
	Female	358	66.2	15.6		

Note: At 5% level of significance the table value of t-value is 1.96; NS- Not Significant

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between male and female higher secondary commerce students in their emotional intelligence and achievement in commerce since the calculated t-values (0.478 & 1.46) are less than the table t-value (1.96).. Hence the null hypothesis is retained.

- H₀3: There is no significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary commerce students in their emotional intelligence and academic achievement.

Table 3: Difference between rural and urban higher secondary students in their emotional intelligence and academic achievement

Variable	Locality of Students	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Remarks
Emotional Intelligence	Rural	254	148.6	19.4	0.653	NS
	Urban	596	156.9	17.5		
Achievement in Commerce	Rural	254	67.7	12.5	1.42	NS
	Urban	596	71.3	11.9		

Note: At 5% level of significance the table value of t-value is 1.96; NS- Not Significant

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between male and female higher secondary commerce students in their emotional intelligence and achievement in commerce since the calculated t-values (0.653 & 1.42) are less than the table t-value (1.96). Hence the null hypothesis is retained.

Correlation Analysis:

H₀4: There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of higher secondary commerce students.

Table 4: Relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement in commerce of higher secondary students

Variables		Sub samples		N	Calculated 'r' value	Table 'r' value	Remarks
Emotional Intelligence	Academic achievement in commerce	Gender	Male	492	0.342	0.062	Significant Positive Correlation
			Female	358	0.261		
		Locality of Students	Rural	254	0.243	0.062	Significant Positive Correlation
			Urban	596	0.299		

It is inferred from the above table that there is significant positive relationship between emotional intelligence and achievement in commerce of higher secondary students,

Findings of the Study:

The major findings derived from the study are:

1. The level of emotional intelligence and academic achievement in commerce of male and female higher secondary commerce students are found to be average.
2. No significant difference was found between male and female higher secondary commerce students in their emotional intelligence and academic achievement.
3. No significant difference was found between rural and urban higher secondary commerce students in their emotional intelligence and academic achievement.
4. There is significant positive relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of higher secondary commerce students.

Conclusion:

The findings of the study that the level of emotional intelligence and academic achievement in commerce of male and female higher secondary commerce students are found to be average, makes the commerce teachers and students feel the need to boost up their spirit to reach high level. The chosen variables of study are found to be not affected on the basis of gender and locality of the students, giving the hope that apart from these factors the students can do better in their emotional intelligence and achievement in commerce. The positive correlation that exists between these variables exposes the need to promote them by organizing seminars, workshops and other related efforts for the overall benefit of the community of commerce higher secondary students.

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